

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 7, No. 10; October 28, 2001

Dear Readers:

This issue contains another three interesting papers: I do hope you will enjoy them ... and be encouraged to submit a paper yourself.

J.UCS now has gone through some "facelifting": I hope you like the new design! Comments (positive or others) are welcome...and you can attach them right here by clicking the "Write" button. Even better, if you write a comment, I will automatically get an email notification that you sent a comment, so that I can immediately check on it. If you type in your email address in the comment dialogue you will also be notified if there are any replies to your comment. Have a look at how this works by going to http://www.jucs.org/jucs_7_9/editorial and then clicking on READ!

The search facility is now also much improved and simplified: you can search by author or do a fulltext search of material in any year, or over all years. This is just one of the many new features we are about to present, making J.UCS one of the most (if not THE most) state-of-the-art electronic journal.

Enjoy this issue, and make sure your university has subscribed to J.UCS so that everyone on your campus can easily access all papers without the need for name or password.

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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